

PROTECTIVE EFFECT OF MANGOSTEEN SKIN EXTRACT ON ALBINO MICE SKIN WITH DIMETHYL-BENZ(A)ANTHRACENE (DMBA) INDUCTION: ANALYSIS ON P53 PROTEIN LEVEL

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Skin cancer is the most common type of malignancy in humans with a dramatic incidence increase in the past decade. One of the genes that may play a role in carcinogenesis is p53 gene. Mangosteen skin extract contains xanthone derivatives, such as α -, β -, and γ -mangostins, which are known to possess anticancer property. Despite its well documented use in other types of carcinoma, its effect in skin tumor carcinogenesis is still unknown. **Methods:** This experimental study was done in 30 mice randomly assigned into groups receiving different treatments. The positive control group received Dimethyl-Benz(a)anthracene (DMBA), a potent carcinogen, induction while the treatment groups received mangosteen skin extract with 100, 200, and 400 ppm concentrations. The protein p53 level from skin tumor in each mouse was assessed using ELISA. **Result:** Protein p53 level was highest in the positive control group while the lowest value was shown by the group with 100 ppm extract application. One-way ANOVA test showed a significant difference across groups ($p=0.000$). Least significant difference post-hoc analysis showed a significantly lower protein p53 levels of both 100 ppm and 400 ppm mangosteen skin extract compared to the DMBA control group ($p=0.000$). **Conclusion:** This study showed that topical application of mangosteen skin extract provided protective effect to skin tumor in mice, possibly through its antioxidant effects. This finding may expand potential future therapeutic options in treating skin cancers.

KEYWORDS DMBA, mangosteen skin extract, p53, skin cancer

Introduction

Skin cancer is by far the most common type of malignancy in humans and its incidence is found to increase dramatically in the past years.[1], [2] In the United States, the number of patients with skin cancer showed a more significant increase compared to other types of cancer. In Asia, the incidence of skin cancer is approximately 2-4%.[3] This increase is thought to be associated with the increasing number of geriatric population and high ultraviolet (UV) radiation as a result of ozone layer depletion.[4] Skin cancer is characterized by a low apoptosis rate or high cell proliferation and epidermal cell turnover. Although UV radiation is the main etiology of skin cancer, other agents such as

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virus, chemical mutagen, and genetic susceptibility, are also postulated to hold a pivotal role in carcinogenesis. Most cancer cells survive by avoiding apoptosis or present defective apoptosis mechanism which leads to uncontrolled cell division.[5]

One of the genes that may play a role in carcinogenesis is p53. This gene is activated once stimuli such as DNA damage, hypoxia, and oncogene activation take place. As a transcription factor, p53 mediates changes in gene expression that support cell protection, such as apoptosis, senescence, or DNA repair. These three mechanisms are central to protection against cancer development.[6]

Mangosteens, with the scientific name *Garcinia mangostana*, have been bred and used as traditional herbal medicine for centuries in tropical countries, especially in Asia. mangosteen skin extract contains xanthone derivatives, such as α -, β -, and γ -mangostins, which are known to possess inhibitory effects to colon carcinoma cells. Furthermore, DNA electrophoresis analysis has shown that α -mangostin has anti apoptosis effect.[7] In addition, studies have also shown strong anti-proliferative effect in combating leukemia cells in HL60 cells. Interestingly, α -mangostin is also capable of inducing mitochondrial dysfunction which results in cell cycle cessation and apoptosis in DLD-1 colon cancer cells.[8]

Although the benefit of mangosteen skin extract as antioxidant and anti-proliferative have been acknowledged in various diseases, the protective effect of the topical mangosteen skin extract against carcinogenesis is still unknown. This study aims to examine the expression of p53 protein in mice with tumours induced with DMBA, Dimethyl-Benz(a)anthracene, a potent carcinogen.

Material and Methods

Study Design, Subjects and Treatment

This was an experimental study with post-test control design where subjects were randomly assigned into six groups (group I until VI). Every group consisted of 5 albino mice with the age of 6-9 weeks with normal diet. Group I and group II served as the negative and positive control group. No treatment was given to group I (negative control) while group II was given DMBA induction (positive control). Group III was given both DMBA induction and ethanol, which was the mangosteen extract solvent. The treatment groups were divided into three groups, group IV, group V, and group VI, where each group was given DMBA induction and 100 ppm, 200 ppm, and 400 ppm mangosteen skin extract, respectively.

DMBA induction was done three times a week while topical mangosteen skin extract or ethanol application was done daily. In subjects with DMBA induction and topical mangosteen skin extract or ethanol application, DMBA was applied 20 minutes after topical mangosteen skin extract or ethanol application. This treatment was done for 12 weeks, and 24 hours after the last application, the mice were sacrificed, and the tumour tissue was taken and reserved in a tube filled with normal saline buffer solution for p53 protein analysis with ELISA method.

The study mentioned above protocol has obtained ethical approval from Hasanuddin University Ethical Board Committee (register number UH16121255).

Mangosteen Skin Extraction

Laboratory examination showed that each gram of mangosteen extract consisted of 2.8 mg alpha mangostin. The extraction

Fig.1. The level of p53 protein in each group

process was done by diluting 320 mg mangosteen skin extract in 96% ethanol solution until a volume of 200 ml to obtain a concentration of 1600 ppm (particle per million) (Solution A). From solution A, a volume of 100 ml was taken and was added with 96% ethanol solution until a volume 200 ml to reach a concentration of 800 ppm (solution B). From solution B, a volume of 100 ml was taken and was added with 96% ethanol solution until a volume of 200 ml to reach a concentration of 400 ppm (solution C). From solution C, a volume of 100 ml was taken and was added with 96% ethanol solution until a volume of 200 ml to reach a concentration of 200 ppm (solution D). From solution D, a volume of 100 ml was taken and was added with 96% ethanol solution until a volume of 200 ml to reach a concentration of 100 ppm (solution E). Solution C (400 ppm), D (200 ppm), and E (100 ppm) were used in this study.

P53 protein Analysis Using ELISA

Tumour tissue was ground and put into a tube filled with saline buffer solution. Centrifugation with a speed of 3000 rpm was run for 20 minutes and the supernatant solution formed was taken for ELISA with the commercial kits (Cat#KMC0012 for IL-1 β) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Data Analysis

The result of p53 protein measurement was analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 23.0 for Windows (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA). The analysis method used were normality tests (Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk), one-way ANOVA test, and post-hoc least significance difference (LSD).

Result

This study examined the p53 protein level in six groups of mice with different treatments. The positive control group showed the highest p53 protein level with a mean of 1.548 ± 0.07727 ng/ml while the lowest value was shown by group IV (mean value of 1.2100 ± 0.05385 ng/ml). One-way ANOVA test showed a significant difference across groups ($p=0.000$) (Figure 1).

Least significant difference post-hoc analysis showed a significant difference between both 100 ppm and 400 ppm mangosteen extract with DMBA control group ($p=0.000$), with a better result shown by the 100-ppm extract.

Discussion

This study evaluates the anticancer effect of mangosteen skin extract by measuring the level of p53 protein in mice given DMBA induction. The data showed that p53 protein level in DMBA control group was significantly higher compared to the treatment groups. The high p53 protein level reflected the cellular DNA damage caused by DMBA. The 100 ppm mangosteen extract group showed the lowest p53 protein level.

Previous studies indicated that Mangosteen extract possesses potent antioxidant activity due to the variety of antioxidant components, such as phenolic acid, flavonoids, epicatechin, anthocyanins, proanthocyanidins, and xanthenes.[9] It is the antioxidant effects mediated by these substances which are postulated to inhibit reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation in this study, which resulted in less cell damage in the treatment group. Therefore, the p53 protein level in these groups was lower compared to the positive control group. This result showed that mangosteen skin extract provides a protective effect against DMBA-induced cell damage which is not mediated through the p53 signalling pathway.

Several studies have demonstrated the anticancer property of α -mangostin in other types of cancer. It is interesting to see that the anticancer property of α -mangostin seems to vary among studies depending on the cancer cells. A study by Kritsanawong et al. showed that α -mangostin induced apoptosis associated with HER2/PI3K/Akt and MAPK signalling pathways on breast cancer cells.[10] Another study on colon cancer cells showed the apoptosis-inducing property of α -mangostin via both extrinsic and intrinsic pathways.[11]

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to demonstrate the protective effect of topical application of mangosteen skin extract on DMBA-induced mice skin cancer. The data in this study suggested that its antioxidant effects mediate this effect instead by the p53 signalling pathway. Further studies examining the antioxidant status are required to elucidate the anticancer property of mangosteen skin extract in skin cancer.

Conclusion

This study showed that topical application of mangosteen skin extract provided a protective effect to a skin tumour in mice, possibly through its antioxidant effects. This finding may expand potential future therapeutic options in treating skin cancers.

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